

second-instar larvae per hill on plants at 40, 60, and 80 d after seeding (DAS). Infested plots were enclosed with open fiberglass cages to prevent larvae from dispersing.

The leaf area damaged by LF larvae was higher on plants at 40 DAS than on plants at 60 and 80 DAS (see table). Leaf consumption, based on actual leaf area damage, was incorporated into the model. Simulation runs were made for each larval density and crop age. (See figure for the simulated leaf area and simulated yield at different larval densities and crop ages.) The model predicted 9, 12, and 30% leaf area reduction on plants at 80, 60, and 40 DAS, respectively, when infested with 20 larvae. Crop response to insect damage seemed to decrease with crop age. The predicted yield reduction was only 3.4% on plants at 40 DAS infested with 20 larvae. The simulated yield reduction was $\leq 1\%$ on plants at 80 and 60 DAS infested with up to 33 larvae. In most ricefields, LF larval populations are rarely more than two per hill.

The results suggest that leaf consumption of 20 larvae seems insufficient to significantly reduce crop yield. This may

Simulated leaf area (a) and simulated yield (b) at different larval densities and crop ages.

Weekly mean leaf area damage on plants infested ($\pm$ SE) by LF at different crop ages.

Sampling time (wk)	Damaged leaf area (cm ²)/hill		
	40 DAS ^a	60 DAS	80 DAS
1	4.52 $\pm$ 0.16	2.58 $\pm$ 0.09	1.99 $\pm$ 0.06
2	10.69 $\pm$ 0.28	6.08 $\pm$ 0.29	4.64 $\pm$ 0.12
3	9.12 $\pm$ 0.33	6.53 $\pm$ 0.22	4.41 $\pm$ 0.04

^aDAS = days after seeding.

be attributed to the rice plant's ability to compensate for damage at early stages. In addition, photosynthesis rates in different leaf layers may increase as a result of damage. Although MACROS

does not have these compensatory components, yield losses predicted were extremely low. Thus, it appears that LF can rarely cause significant yield losses in farmers' fields. ■

Pest resistance

Resistance of Guangxi wild rice to diseases and insect pests

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Oryza rufipogon and *O. officinalis* are the two kinds of wild rice in Guangxi Province, China. The Institute of Crop Germplasm Resources under the Guangxi Academy of Agricultural Sciences and the Institute of Plant Protection under the Guangxi Agricultural College have cooperated since 1981 to evaluate these wild rices for resistance to blast (BI), bacterial blight (BB), brown planthopper (BPH),

whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and gall midge (GM) (Table 1).

Of the available accessions, the following are resistant to a particular pest: 23 *O. rufipogon* and 15 *O. officinalis* to BI; 16 *O. rufipogon* and 11 *O. officinalis* to Chinese BB races I-V; 20 *O. rufipogon* to BPH biotypes 1 and 2 (86 *O. officinalis* are highly resistant to BPH); 117 *O. officinalis* to WPBH, with 47 possessing very high resistance; and 8 *O. rufipogon* and 1 *O. officinalis* to GM. These accessions have been recommended as donors of resistance in the national rice breeding program (Table 2). They are conserved in the Nanning Wild Rice Nursery. ■

Table 1. Wild rice resistance to diseases and insect pests.

Species	Disease/insect pest	Accessions evaluated (no.)	Resistant accessions	
			no.	%
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Blast	1587	67	4.1
	Bacterial blight	1553	289	18.6
	Brown planthopper	1214	30	2.5
	Whitebacked planthopper	1236	27	2.2
	Gall midge	1203	8	1.4
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Blast	199	22	11.0
	Bacterial blight	199	194	97.5
	Brown planthopper	198	195	98.5
	Whitebacked planthopper	197	197	100.0
	Gall midge	184	1	0.5

Table 2. Accessions with resistance to diseases and insect pests. Nanning, Guangxi, China.

Resistance	Accession
Blast	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : YD.2-0417, 0418, 0435, 0452, 0453, 0528, 0538, 0555, 0578, 0583, 0587, 0590, 0591, 0593, 0618, 0797, 0854, 0971, 1010, 1263, 1314, 1360, 1372 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1618, 1624, 1626, 1627, 1628, 1629, 1635, 1645, 1647, 1674, 1680, 1698, 1724, 1737, 1764
Bacterial blight	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : YD.2-0078, 0233, 0314, 0317, 0321, 0339, 0349, 0369, 0480, 0684, 0764, 0795, 0842, 1162, 1470, 1504 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1630, 1656, 1667, 1668, 1669, 1670, 1685, 1702, 1703, 1719, 1721
Brown planthopper	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : N-0471, 0513, STS-543, 2167, 2172, 2173, 2182, 2184, 2190, 2205 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1665, 1694, 1738, 1594, 1597, 1608, 1609, 1611, 1612, 1613, 1616, 1617, 1618, 1623, 1624, 1630, 1632, 1633, 1646, 1649, 1650, 1651, 1652, 1654, 1655, 1656, 1658, 1659, 1660, 1661
Whitebacked planthopper	<i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1592, 1593, 1594, 1595, 1596, 1608, 1609, 1641, 1642, 1643, 1661, 1671, 1673, 1674, 1675, 1684, 1685, 1686, 1692, 1694, 1695, 1696, 1697, 1698, 1701, 1702, 1703, 1704, 1712, 1713
Gall midge	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : YD.2-0352, 0686, 0869, 0899, 1296, 1373, 1422, 1536 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1751

Pest resistance—diseases

Resistance to rice blast in a line derived from *Oryza minuta*

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Oryza minuta, a wild species of rice, is highly resistant to rice blast (BI). A line derived from a wide cross between *O. minuta* and an elite *O. sativa* breeding line, IR31917-45-3-2, hereafter referred to as *OsS*, was found to possess BI resistance. Genetic studies of this line have shown that a single gene confers resistance to isolate *PO6-6* of *Pyricularia oryzae*.

During initial screening, plants were artificially inoculated with isolate *PO6-6*, and disease reactions were scored on a 0-5 scale (Table 1). Although resistance was dominant over susceptibility, under

highly favorable conditions for BI development the homozygotes (RR) were significantly more resistant than the heterozygotes (Rr) using the *t*-test ($P < 0.001$). The mean disease rating for RR plants was 1.8 ± 0.6 (mean $\pm$ SD, $n = 21$), while that of the Rr group was 2.8 ± 1.1 ($n = 34$). To characterize this resistance further, we evaluated a homozygous line, hereafter referred to as *NIL127*, in greenhouse and field studies under upland conditions. *NIL127* was shown to be nearly isogenic to *OsS* based on analysis using molecular markers (less than 1% introgression of markers from the wild species).

To assess the resistance in *NIL127* with respect to pathogen lineages, we inoculated it with 49 isolates of *P. oryzae* representing lineages 1, 4, 7, 9, 10, 11, and 14. (A lineage is a group of isolates inferred to be related by descent, based on DNA fingerprinting and phylogenetic analysis.) In this test, each treatment consisted of a pot of 12 seedlings per line. Seedlings were inoculated by spraying with a spore suspension (10^5 spores/ml) at 21 d after sowing (dry

seeded). After inoculation, plants were incubated for 24 h at 24 °C and 100% relative humidity, then transferred to a mist room at 24 °C under natural light for 5 d. Disease reactions were scored (Table 1). Each treatment was replicated twice.

Of the 49 isolates tested, 32 (representing lineages 4, 7, and 14) were compatible on recurrent parent *OsS* (Table 1). *OsS* was not susceptible to any test isolates of lineages 1, 9, 10, or 11. *NIL127* was resistant to all test isolates of

Table 1. Characterization of *NIL127* BI resistance with respect to *P. oryzae* lineages 4, 7, and 14.

Lineage ^a	Isolate	Disease reaction ^b	
		<i>OsS</i>	<i>NIL127</i>
4	Ca1	4	0
4	Ca9	4	0
4	Ca13	3	0
4	Ca19	4	0
4	Ca27	4	0
4	Ca30	4	0
4	Ca33	4	0
4	Ca40	4	0
4	Ca42	4	0
4	Ca44	4	0
4	Ca48	4	0
4	Ca51	4	0
4	Ca52	4	4
4	Ca70	4	2
4	Ca72	4	0
4	Ca73	4	0
4	Ca74	4	0
4	Ca77	4	0
4	Ca78	4	0
4	Ca79	4	0
4	Ca80	4	4
4	Ca81	4	4
4	Ca83	4	2
4	Ca84	4	0
4	Ca87	4	0
4	Ca89	4	0
4	Ca90	4	0
4	Ca91	4	0
4	Ca93	4	0
7	BN105	4	0
7	BN117	4	0
14	BN113	4	0

^aLineage as determined by DNA fingerprinting using the probe MGR586. ^bDefinition of disease reactions: 0 = immune, no evidence of infection; 1 = resistant, with brown specks, no sporulation; 2 = moderately resistant, 1- to 2-mm long, irregularly shaped lesions with brown margins; 3 = intermediate, 5 or less, 3- to 7-mm long typical, spindle-shaped sporulating lesions per inoculated leaf; 4 = susceptible, 5 or more typical lesions per inoculated leaf, lesions often coalesce; 5 = highly susceptible, many coalesced lesions infecting 50% or more of inoculated leaf, leaf dies because of lesions.